

Statement on carnivore research carried out in southwestern Hungary

Research group: One Health Working Group (Kaposvár Campus of Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences)

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During our research activities, we process specimens of wild carnivores hunted legally under the regulation of Hungarian and European law. We investigate faecal samples and/or carcasses of carnivores belonging to the species as follows: European polecat (*Mustela putorius*), beech marten (*Martes foina*), European badger (*Meles meles*), red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*), golden jackal (*Canis aureus*), common muskrat (*Ondatra zibethicus*), racoon dog (*Nyctereutes procyonoides*), racoon (*Procyon lotor*), hooded crow (*Corvus cornix*), magpie (*Pica pica*), and Eurasian jay (*Garrulus glandarius*).

Since our specimens originate from legal hunting carried out in accordance with a national population reduction programme (detailed below) and independent of our research purposes, the **ARRIVE guidelines 2.0** (see <https://arriveguidelines.org/sites/arrive/files/documents/ARRIVE%20guidelines%202.0%20-%20English.pdf>, accessed 12 June 2025) cannot be followed during study planning. In particular, the sample size determination is impossible in advance. The referred document claims that "*The guidelines are relevant to any study involving live animals, from mammals to fish, as well as invertebrates, in any area of the biosciences*" in section "Introducing ARRIVE 2.0" paragraph 2. Therefore, we interpreted the intention of the ARRIVE guidelines 2.0 as being for the welfare and responsible use of live animals during research activities. We work on dead carcasses assigned to our Working Group by wildlife managers, whose hunting activities are regulated by law and authorities (see below).

Of the above-mentioned species, exclusively the golden jackal (*Canis aureus*), and the European polecat (*Mustela putorius*) is referred in Annex V of **Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora** as "*of community interest whose taking in the wild and exploitation may be subject to management measures*". See <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/1992/43/oj/eng> (accessed on 12 June 2025)

All investigated species, i.e. European polecat (*Mustela putorius*), beech marten (*Martes foina*), European badger (*Meles meles*), red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*), golden jackal

(*Canis aureus*), common muskrat (*Ondatra zibethicus*), racoon dog (*Nyctereutes procyonoides*), racoon (*Procyon lotor*), hooded crow (*Corvus cornix*), magpie (*Pica pica*), and Eurasian jay (*Garrulus glandarius*), are listed in 1. § (1) bb) section of **79/2004. (V. 4.) FVM* Regulation** as "other small-sized wildlife". (**Regulation on the implementation of Act on wildlife protection, wildlife management, and hunting no. 1996/LV*) See <https://njt.hu/jogszabaly/2004-79-20-82.50> (in Hungarian, accessed on 12 June 2025)

Annex 6 of **79/2004. (V. 4.) FVM Regulation** orders that the wildlife manager of a certain wildlife unit should submit a wildlife management plan to the Wildlife Management Authority annually, which should contain "*The viewpoints and methods of carnivore managements*" (see 6.3 point of the Annex).

Based on Annex 7 of **79/2004. (V. 4.) FVM Regulation**, the Wildlife Management Authority prescribe the level of population control for carnivore species of European polecat (*Mustela putorius*), beech marten (*Martes foina*), European badger (*Meles meles*), red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*), golden jackal (*Canis aureus*), common muskrat (*Ondatra zibethicus*), racoon dog (*Nyctereutes procyonoides*), racoon (*Procyon lotor*), hooded crow (*Corvus cornix*), magpie (*Pica pica*), and Eurasian jay (*Garrulus glandarius*).

Annex 7 orders that the regional chief hunter is obliged to check the fulfilment of the prescribed control programme. In case of default, the Wildlife Management Authority shall impose a penalty upon the wildlife manager.

In **Regulation 10/2018. (VII. 3.) AM**, point 8. prescribes the *basic principles on wildlife management planning in South Transdanubia* (see <https://njt.hu/jogszabaly/2018-10-20-7R>, in Hungarian, accessed on 12 June 2025), as follows:

8.1. Primary goal is population reduction of wild carnivores allowed to be hunted (not protected).

8.2. In the case of the red fox, at least 1.5× of the estimated spring population should be removed from the hunting area. 60% of the planned population reduction should be carried out during the first half of the year.

8.3. In the case of the European badger, the goal is to impede the population expansion, therefore at least 0.5-0.7× population reduction rate should be applied.

8.4. In South Transdanubia, all observed individuals of the racoon dog and the racoon should be removed.

8.5. In the case of the golden jackal, the goal is to impede the colonisation of the whole region; therefore, a 2.0× population reduction rate should be applied.